

Interaction of paraquat with electrochemically synthesized silver nanoparticles

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Manuscript received 11 May 2007, accepted 21 May 2007

Abstract : A diffuse reflectance Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (DRS-FTIR) was applied for the study of interaction of paraquat (1,1'-dimethyl-4,4'-bipyridylium cation), one of the most commonly used pesticides, with electrochemically synthesized silver nanoparticles. It is based on simple chemical treatment of paraquat with silver nanoparticles prepared by electrochemical method. The adsorption of paraquat on the surface of nanoparticles occurs resulting in particle agglomeration, which is indicated by hypsochromic shift (~30 nm) in the electronic spectra of silver nanoparticle solution. FTIR spectra of the paraquat treated with silver nanoparticles shows partial or complete disappearance of certain peaks which are found in case of pure paraquat.

Keywords : Paraquat, nanoparticles, silver.

In recent years, a significant increase in the use of pesticides against agricultural pests has been observed in India and rest of the world. One of the major reasons for the increase is the ease of using pesticides and ensuring an absolute result. Paraquat (1,1'-dimethyl-4,4'-bipyridylium cation), a weed killer, is one of the most stable pesticides known and has been detected in the environment. It is an active component of commercial aqueous preparation known as gramoxone and methyl viologen¹⁻³. Paraquat is highly toxic to man and is a poison with no known antidote. Paraquat poisoning includes severe lung damage in human beings. The mechanisms of toxic effects of paraquat are largely the result of a metabolically catalyzed single electron reduction-oxidation reaction resulting in depletion of cellular NADPH and the generation of potentially toxic form of oxygen such as superoxide radical (O_2^-)⁴. Generation of O_2^- leads to formation of more toxic forms of reduced oxygen and hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2) and hydroxyl radical (OH^*). Hydroxyl radicals have been implicated in the initiation of membrane damaging by lipid per oxidation, inactivation of proteins and causing damage to DNA. Depletion of NADPH may disrupt important NADPH requiring biological processes such as fatty acid synthesis^{5,6}.

Particles with at least one dimension (d) < 100 nm are termed as nanoparticles. Metal nanoparticles with controlled size and shape are of great interest because of their morphology dependent properties⁷. Nanomaterials have unique physical and chemical properties that offer important possibilities for analytical chemistry. They have significant potential for a wide range of applications such as catalysis, magnetic recording media, optoelectronic materials, magnetic fluids, composite materials. Their uniqueness arises from their high ratio of surface area to volume (aspect ratio) as these materials typically have diameter of 100 nm or less. Metal particles in the nanometer size range can serve as efficient catalyst⁸ in many redox reactions due to the fact that they possess a large surface area that acts as a substrate on which the electron transfer reaction occurs⁹. There are several physical/chemical processes for the production of nanoparticles. Nanoparticles prepared by physical methods possess clean surfaces and uniform particle size distribution. However, industrial applications are limited due to low production rates and high cost. Chemical methods are generally not applied to the production of metallic nanoparticles. All properties of a material change as the particle size approaches molecular dimensions and because it is often the unique properties of the nanoparticle that make it useful for the practical purpose, this is why the properties of nanoparticle differ from those of bulk samples. Hence an electrochemical process is applied for the synthesis of nanoparticle which is rapid, low cost and has

uniform particle size distribution. Electrochemically prepared nanoparticles acts as better catalyst than prepared by other methods¹⁰. Both silver and gold nanoparticles catalyze the redox reaction but the extent of reaction is different¹¹. Silver nanoparticle served better than gold (in terms of enhancing the rate of reduction). In view of these, we thought it is important to investigate the possible use of metal nanoparticles in degradation and thus detoxifying paraquat.

This study describes that paraquat can be interacted by noble metal nanoparticles prepared by electrochemical method. A new electrochemical method for preparation of silver nanoparticles is also described in this paper. The homogeneously ($\sim 5\text{--}9$ nm) synthesized silver nanoparticle has an advantage of being smaller in size and produced rapidly in comparison to chemical methods. The chemistry of pesticide degradation occurs in a wide concentration range of environmental significance and the process may be scaled up for environmental degradation etc. The chemical procedures involved are simple, less time consuming and can be adapted in any environment making it a practical technology. This method showed more effectiveness with silver nanoparticles as compared to gold nanoparticles.

Results and discussion

Fig. 1 shows the TEM image of silver nanoparticle prepared electrochemically as discussed below. TEM characterized the size and shape of the nanoparticle. The TEM spectrum shows the formation of nearly spherical

Fig. 1. TEM images of silver nanoparticle sample ($\sim 5\text{--}9$ nm) synthesized electrochemically (1.0×10^{-4} M AgNO_3 , 2.0×10^{-4} M sodium citrate in final dilution).

and homogeneously distributed silver nanoparticle in the dimension range 5–9 nm. The particle size dependency and stability were also checked by application of varying potential differences across the electrode pair, time for electrolysis and quantity of stabilizer used. A potential difference range of 3.0–5.0 V across the Pt-electrode pair, electrolysis time of 15–20 min, $(1.5\text{--}3.5) \times 10^{-4}$ M sodium citrate in a final solution of 20 mL, and the use of stabilizing agent i.e. glycerol and ethanol in 1 : 1 ratio were found suitable for full reduction of 20 mL of 1.0×10^{-4} M AgNO_3 to produce homogeneously distributed and stable nanoparticles of silver. The silver nanoparticles so prepared has particle dimension of $\sim 5\text{--}9$ nm with the maximum absorption of the plasmon at 420 nm. The particles were found stable for atleast 72 h at room temperature i.e. at 25 ± 2 °C. Small particles have a more negative potential¹¹ and larger surface area that provides the sufficient and necessary condition for the electron transfer processes to take place. It was found that electrochemically prepared silver nanoparticle acts as a better catalyst than photochemically prepared ones.

Fig. 2 presents the UV-visible spectra of silver nanoparticles after exposure to paraquat solutions of different concentrations. The concentrations were 2, 10, 100 and 500 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ and the spectra were recorded after 2 h of the addition of paraquat. The adsorption of paraquat on the surface of nanoparticles occurs resulting in particle

Fig. 2. Effect of paraquat on spectral properties of silver nanoparticles ($\sim 5\text{--}7$ nm).

agglomeration, which is indicated by hypsochromic shift in the electronic spectra of silver nanoparticle solution. The plasmon absorption at 420 nm decreases in intensity after 2 h upon addition and an additional peak emerges at shorter wavelengths. Dampening and shift of the plasmon indicate adsorbate binding on the nanoparticle surface or it can be said that the shift in the plasmon can be attributed to adsorption of paraquat on the surface of silver nanoparticles. It is evident from the figure that the interaction is distinctly stronger at lower concentration of paraquat; in addition to shifts this provide a smooth decrease in intensity relative to pure silver nanoparticle, however higher concentration of paraquat shows a shoulder at certain wavelengths which concludes that better adsorption at nanoparticle surface occurs at lower concentration of paraquat possibly due to rapid using up of nanoparticles by paraquat molecules at high concentration thus leaving lesser number of nanoparticles for interaction. This method showed a very strong interaction with silver nanoparticles and the shifts were also remarkable (30 nm), but in contrast, comparing the adsorption, this method showed a very weak interaction with gold nanoparticles and the shifts were also very weak (15 nm). The relatively higher shift observed with silver nanoparticles in the present work may be due to availability of comparatively large surface area provided by relatively smaller particle size for adsorption. Thus, keeping in mind, the experimental cost and time present method is more suitable and rapid.

Fig. 3 shows the Fourier transform infrared spectrum of pure and the nanoparticle treated paraquat. The use of

a volume range of 2–5 mL of electrochemically synthesized silver nanoparticle produced a significant change in the structure of paraquat. The change in the structure of paraquat after treatment with silver nanoparticle was seen with a chosen volume of 3 mL of silver nanoparticle, Fig. 3. Infrared spectrum of paraquat is complex, the characteristic absorption occurred at (815, 845, 875), 1180, 1560, 2965, (3018, 3056, 3108) cm^{-1} and have been assigned to aromatic C–H bending vibration, CH_3 scissor, C=C, CH_3 stretching, and O–H stretching, respectively. Upon adsorption on the silver nanoparticles the features changed substantially and almost all the peaks appeared weakly.

Experimental

UV-visible spectra were recorded with Carl Zeiss Jena 'Spekol' spectrophotometer fitted with an EK-5 unit and matched glass cells of 1-cm optical path length. FTIR spectra were recorded using Diffuse Reflectance FTIR (DRS-FTIR) Spectrometer (Shimadzu 8400S, Kyoto, Japan) equipped with L-Alanine Doped Deuterated Triglycine Sulphate (ADTGS) detector. Qualigens micropipette with disposable tips was used.

All chemicals and reagents used were of analytical grade (B.D.H./Merck). All aqueous solutions were prepared in double distilled water. The experiment was performed with electrochemically prepared silver nanoparticles.

A 1×10^{-4} M AgNO_3 and 2×10^{-2} M sodium citrate was used for synthesis of Ag-nanoparticles. Glycerol and ethanol in 1 : 1 ratio was used as stabilizing agent. Stock

Fig. 3. Comparison of infrared spectra of (a) pure paraquat residue ($100 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$), (b) paraquat ($100 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) after reaction with silver nanoparticle (3 mL).

solution of paraquat ($1000 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) was prepared in ethanol and was diluted to the required concentration with the same solvent. The paraquat solution was mixed with nanoparticle solution in water to get the reported concentration.

Procedure for synthesis of silver nanoparticle : $1.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M AgNO}_3$ (20 mL) is taken in a 50 mL beaker. To this a mixture of glycerol and ethanol in 1 : 1 ratio as stabilizing agent is added which is followed by the drop wise addition of $2.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ M}$ sodium citrate (0.2 mL) during stirring of the final solution. The electrolysis of the solution is then carried out using a pair of Pt-electrodes ($1.5 \times 5.0 \text{ cm}^2$) placed at 1-cm apart from each other and kept at a potential difference between +3.0 to +5.0 V. The electrical connectivity of the electrodes is carried through mercury in the tube (Fig. 4). Stirring of the electrolyte is carried out using a small DC-battery (+3.0 V) operating stirrer, fabricated by the use of an ordinary toy-motor. The electrolysis is performed for 15–20 min. The formation of silver nanoparticle is confirmed by the appearance of clear yellow solution.

Fig. 4. Arrangement of electrolytic cell containing mixture of silver nitrate ($1.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$) and sodium citrate ($2.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$) in a final dilution.

Procedure for treatment of paraquat with nanoparticles : The chemical stability of paraquat was tested upon treatment with nanoparticles for 1–8 h. Stock solution of paraquat ($1000 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) was prepared in ethanol and was diluted to the 2, 10, 100 and $500 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ concentrations with the same solvent. The 0.2 mL paraquat solutions of different concentrations were then mixed with 3 mL nanoparticle solution. The spectra were then recorded after 2 h of addition of paraquat. Subsequent

spectra were then recorded for 8 h and the results were found to be the same. Compositions of all the solutions in a set of studies were the same, except for paraquat.

Procedure for FTIR analysis : The above samples were then analyzed by DRS-FTIR. To prepare the samples for analysis, 0.5 mL of each of the concentration of nanoparticle treated paraquat was mixed with 1 g finely ground IR grade KBr. It was then evaporated in a water bath. The sample was then taken in a stainless steel cuvette and run for IR spectra. Subsequently pure paraquat ($1000 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) with KBr after evaporation is then run for IR spectra. Spectra were collected by averaging 45 scans at the range of 4000 to 400 cm^{-1} at resolution of 4 cm^{-1} . KBr is used as substrate as it provides analytical window in whole range of operation¹². Diffuse reflectance technique was used due to its non-destructive and time saving properties. Furthermore, samples can be recovered back for other advanced analysis. The apodization used was Happ-Genzel. The internal beam was used with mirror speed 2.8 mm s^{-1} in the FTIR.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to the Prof. Rama Pande, Head, School of Studies in Chemistry, and Prof. Shailendra Sharaf, Director, Institute of Pharmacy, Pt. Ravishankar Shukla University, Raipur, India for providing laboratory facilities. Authors are also thankful to the UGC, New Delhi for funding.

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